

NEW DIRECTIONS IN SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL SUPERVISION DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10359728**Maria José Bestete de Miranda***PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).**mariajosebestete@yahoo.com.br.***Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza***PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).**srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.***Evandro Carlos Salerno***PhD student in Educational Sciences; Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences (FICS).**evandronorne@hotmail.com.***ABSTRACT**

This article addresses the topic of new directions in the practice of educational School Supervision. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it explores the dynamics and pragmaticity linked to the profession and how it has improved and the new fields that are available for didactic-pedagogical work in which the supervisor can add value and technical-scientific proficiency. Its social relevance lies in offering the broad public a more comprehensive and enlightening view of the supervisor's action in formal educational processes. This is a bibliographical research, based on the authors' praxis and specialized literature on the topic. The school supervisor is the individual who guides, investigates, helps and modifies the way teachers work, without imposition, but with participation. The concepts about the role and the specialist have sought to follow the development of the Supervisor's role and many confuse the technical and administrative aspects. Some stick to the supervision and inspection aspects, as they are perhaps the simplest and have marked the first attempts to structure the Supervisor's role. The Supervisor must be encouraged to discover in the most diverse ways the great importance of his attitudes in determining the quality of his work. As an educational leader, as responsible for the experience of groups at different levels of their activity, he must always reformulate his concepts and must evaluate his performance.

Keywords: School educational supervision; Pedagogical planning; Pedagogical Political Project.

INTRODUCTION

The supervisory function is necessary in any institution that has objective goals to be achieved. The division of labor, the complexity of the instruments and the prediction of what is desired for results constitute requirements for supervisory activity, even because the expression means *a vision that goes beyond, or that lies beyond*; that is, it sees problematic situations, possibilities and/or conflicts that require immediate intervention.

In this sense, the school supervisor is the individual who guides, investigates, helps and modifies the way teachers work, without imposition, but with participation. We are looking for a supervisor committed to learning, a professional who takes care of the pedagogical and didactic part of the school, showing himself capable of integration, of creating a participatory plan, where everyone involved can give their opinion to build paths that lead to the learning process with safety.

Based on the assumption that School Supervision is of fundamental importance in the action of the school community, the following guiding questions were then defined:

- What are the difficulties that lead the school community to develop leadership work?
- How is the development of participatory planning in relation to the School Supervisor's action?
- Does the role of the School Supervisor really enable the school community to integrate and transform its practice in a historical, political and cultural context?

This proposal seeks to contribute to a reflection in order to enable the awareness of professionals involved with school improvement, capable of taking action focused on pedagogical work, in accordance with the needs of the teacher and his *sui generis needs*, both this and the school and other sectors, using appropriate techniques and resources, associating their practice with school-community integration.

THE ORIGIN OF SCHOOL SUPERVISION IN BRAZIL

The idea of Supervision emerged with industrialization, with an interest in improving production, before being taken over by the educational system, in search of better school performance in its educational task. Modern Pedagogy took the model of industrial factories to apply to the administration of the education system, with relative success.

Supervision, in Brazil, emerged with the *Francisco Campos Reform* (1931), through Decree-Law 19,890 of 04/18/1931, conceived in a different way from what had been carried out until that moment. The strictly supervisory character was replaced by the supervisory character, in which this professional's action is taken as part of the educational learning process, guiding professionals, with a view to achieving the best results, efficiently and effectively. From the 1960s and 1970s onwards, supervision was conceived as a pedagogical specialty. The role of the supervisor was no longer that of pure supervision, but of guiding the teacher. Schools needed to be guided in the implementation of teaching programs that met the student's needs, respecting regional characteristics. Furthermore, the supervisory action focuses on the curriculum, with research having an important place in the search for new solutions to improve the quality of teaching.

Law 1971, aNo. 5,692 brought a new educational focus, for the school supervisor he began to gain greater prominence and was absorbed by the job market, his role being essential for the efficiency of teaching. Drawing a parallel between the existing problems in industries, when the need for a supervisor in schools arose, for the emergence of School Supervision, in which pedagogical coordination is constantly mobilized, a framework can be created to facilitate the understanding of the emergence of both, where a surprising similarity can be seen between the two functions.

Table 1 : Comparison between events in Industry and School

Industry	School
Job abandonment	Evasion/repetition/absences
Reluctance to the imposed work rhythm	Not following the class rhythm
Indifference	Apathy in the room
Negligence	Lack of study
Production restrictions	Failure to fulfill the proposed tasks
Overt hostility to administration	Indiscipline in the classroom or at school

Source: Municipal Library “ Heráclides Alves de Araújo” - Muniz Freire – ES, 2023.

In this sense, it is important to remember that, currently, School Supervision cannot be seen as a specialization in methodologies; but, as a much broader function, in which the School Supervisor is an articulator of a Political Pedagogical Project (PPP), together with the entire school community, and cannot lose sight of an investigation of reality, values, relationships of functions in different segments of the school and outside of it, never forgetting that, first and foremost, he is a teacher.

With Law No. 9,394 of 12/20/1996, specific training for school supervision and other technical qualifications is confirmed without considering the successful experiences of training

in Multidisciplinary Pedagogy, which masters with competence all the pedagogical work developed in school. The good performance of the supervisor's role will depend both on the professional's level of competence, as well as on the recognition of this competence by those supervised.

According to Nérici (1978, p. 44) “the Supervisor's role is to diagnose the need, offer suggestions and help, and not observe with a critical spirit what the teacher does or fails to do”. With this, it is clear that the functions of School Supervision are multiple, and it is up to it to coordinate, together with the management, the construction, development and evaluation of the school's pedagogical proposal or PPP (Pedagogical Political Project).

Currently, the work of the school supervisor is extremely important, as he is responsible for the articulation and integration of all content taught in the school unit, in which he carries out an activity of intention, guided by intelligence. Thinking and acting are indispensable, that is, man is a being who is aware that he is capable of transforming reality.

CONCEPT OF SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL SUPERVISION

In this world where paradigm changes are happening very quickly, the concept of teaching requires efficient teacher training. It can be said that the contents, in themselves, have no value, that people and groups are more important than materials... that The quality of teaching is determined more by the teacher, by the type of person he is, by his relationships with others, by his life values, by his knowledge and his insight in interpreting human conduct and the learning process, than by the guides of the teacher. curriculum or other guidelines published by authorities.

Supervision presents itself, firstly, as in-service training. It must make up for the deficiencies in the teacher's technical-pedagogical training, as well as provide means for constant updating. In its modern structure, it brings to its work knowledge about children and the curriculum, an understanding of the role of education in modern life , the ability to work well with groups of individuals and the ability to create situations that make this possible for teachers, as well as efficient help so that they can solve their own problems.

The best characterization of the need for School Supervision is the wealth of contributions it makes when it covers the entire function of education, with the aim of making it more efficient. How does it happen in attempt to establish any concept, it is valid to specify the etymological meaning of the term. The word Supervision is formed by the words *super per* (about) and *vision* (action of seeing). It indicates the attitude of seeing any action more clearly.

As a strict meaning of the term, it can be said that it means looking from above, giving an idea of a global view. In this sense, we can start from a general concept that, in fact, applies to several fields of activity. It is a technical service, of a specialized nature, which involves the skills of an individual, which aims to obtain satisfactory results in the activities of other individuals who are under their control or professional responsibility.

Applying the above to Education, it can be concluded that Supervision is the process by which the School as a whole is guided to achieve its purposes. Muriel Crosby presents in her book *Modern Supervision of Primary Education* (1945), a concept resulting from a consultation with a group of teachers about their expectations regarding good Supervision: “It is a source of resources and a service of leadership and consultation, which helps the School to do its work better” (Id., sp).

It is worth noting that there are many other attempts to conceptualize *Supervision*, both General and, specifically, School. The concepts have sought to follow the development of the Supervisor's role and many confuse the technical and administrative aspects. Some stick to the supervision and inspection aspects, as they are perhaps the simplest and have marked the first attempts to structure the Supervisor's role.

It reduces the breadth of the Supervision function, covering the School as a whole, and, in the second, its main characteristic of guidance, coordination and assistance is highlighted, distinguishing modern Supervision from its traditional concept of inspection and/ or supervision. The change of orientation in the line of practical implementation of Supervision depends on the conceptualization of teaching itself, which has moved away from practices based on mechanistic concepts of learning to use resources more in line with organicist Psychology.

Based on this approach and conception, what extrapolates from many other realities are: the serious problems of access, whether to schools in neighborhoods in large cities or in rural areas, are some of the many original and specific aspects of each educational system, or of each region that integrates a certain system, and must be considered as important variables in determining the Supervision model to be used. A model is understood as a specific form of action designed to achieve change in a given reality.

Considering the variables mentioned, one may doubt whether it is possible to achieve good results, whatever the model. However, what we want to focus on is not the guarantee of good results; rather, the criticism of the use of models taken from other realities, as well as the desire to create an authentic model, having a clear awareness of the reality data that should influence or even determine the type of Supervisor's action. Analyze, for example, how a

Supervisor in the Northeast of Brazil must feel (without being properly informed about the need to change his type of activity), having approximately 100 (one hundred) teaching teachers under his responsibility.

The table below succinctly explains the parallel between the responsibilities of traditional Supervision and those of the current one.

Table 2: Traditional school x Current school

Traditional	Current
Aim for group harmony	Explain contradictions, working on conflict with the aim of establishing working relationships in the school group
Seeking equality in a process masking reality	Working on the differences
Work from your own desire	Work, trying to create demands
Have the same reading for all schools	Reading the school, considering its uniqueness
Produce knowledge models	Create your own forms of knowledge
Emphasize linearized procedures	Emphasize the teacher's production within the school, in a movement of teaching and learning or learning and teaching
Be a facilitator	Be a problematizer
Having knowledge as absolute data	Having knowledge as relative data
Seeing the pedagogical proposal as another form of fad	See in the pedagogical proposal a possibility of rebuilding the school
Have neutral behavior	Clearly express your behavior
Work towards an ideal type of man	Work, keeping in mind the meaning of human life

Source: Municipal Library “ Heráclides Alves de Araújo” - Muniz Freire – ES, 2023.

This transformation from one position to another requires time for the supervisor to change his or her work practices. Analyzing the table above, it can be seen that a first characteristic of the School Supervision process is its complexity , which can be expressed by enumerating some of the many aspects that it can and should assume:

- It is assistance, filling the technical-teaching difficulties observed in the teacher's performance;
- It is a resource, enabling the interpretation of the wishes and needs of the environment ;

- It is a stimulus, allowing the improvement of relationships between all human elements involved in the educational process;
- It is counseling, using greater knowledge of teaching methods and resources basic to the efficiency of school action;
- It is support, analyzing and cooperatively resolving possible difficulties arising from each specific situation;
- It is consultancy, relating the technical-administrative leadership with the operational bases;
- It is co-participation, experiencing the awareness of a single action, aiming for a common objective.

Supervision can also be characterized by understanding the different types of action it involves, as highlighted below:

Philosophical : when it guides the purpose of Education, determining objectives and methods of action, according to basic conceptions of the human person, common good and educational process.

Policy : when it makes the purpose of Education compatible with the true national interests, meeting a specific conception of the State.

Pedagogical : when it equates, through methods and processes suitable, within the philosophical coordinates of a given educational policy, all practical problems of educational action: who to teach; what to teach; when to teach ; how to teach; who will teach.

Supervision is a process that must adapt to the various circumstances of school work . In different modalities of action, it must always identify difficulties, helping teachers to overcome such difficulties through suggestions for appropriate procedures. To meet any diversity of situations, Supervision can take different forms, which can be considered as types of Supervision.

There are authors who have established a classification of these types of Supervision: corrective; preventive; constructive and creative. It is worth remembering that, as with any classification, one must be aware of the need to dissect the characteristics of each type, solely for the sake of study and knowledge. In practice, however, one type is rarely applied in its theoretical purity; there is even a complement, which, in addition to being inevitable, is highly valid.

Corrective supervision: As the name itself indicates , it deals with identifying and locating errors and deficiencies, in order to correct them. It is the closest type to the old concept of Supervision, the autocratic one. It can be considered unscientific, superficial, almost dealing only with symptoms, without deeper investigations into the determining causes. For this reason, it is the easiest, however , it incurs certain risks that must be avoided: treating people and situations as if they were all the same; consider problems in isolation; act in an empirical and perhaps unfair manner; provoke negative emotional attitudes in the teacher.

In general, this type of Supervision is developed when the Supervisor discovers a problem and immediately wants to act to avoid bad consequences. To this end, the teacher warns, indicating the *correct way* to act in the case. A certain importance cannot be denied to this type of Supervision, since, in a broad sense, Supervision always contains some corrective aspect. What, however , seems evident in this type is the inappropriate way to correct, mainly due to the risks it poses. The form of correction most in line with the current concept of Supervision will be the study of the situation, with the cooperative search for a solution, taking into account the specific circumstances of each case.

Preventive supervision: It is also clear from the name itself what is essential for its achievement, avoiding problems before they appear. Its objective is prophylactic, before being therapeutic; prevent rather than cure. Its great advantage is easily understood, especially in maintaining a cooperative work climate and helping the teacher's personal growth.

This type of Supervision cannot always be used as certain problems are unpredictable. It requires a lot of skill from the Supervisor to discover and prognose possible problems that can be avoided by working together. Awareness of its importance and its application can efficiently help the true preparation of teachers, the primary objective of Supervision.

Preventative Supervision meets important aspects required by modern Supervision: Search for solutions in joint work; democratic and scientific action; involvement of a large number of people; special attention to efficient teacher preparation.

Constructive supervision: Its objective is much more the personal and professional development of the teacher than the solution of problems encountered in teaching-learning situations, since most of these problems are caused by deficiencies in the teacher's teaching performance.

To achieve this, the study and analysis of environmental conditions are highly significant; the objectives of Education; educational philosophy; the specific nature of the student and the learning process; teaching methods and processes, etc.

The seriousness of this type of Supervision can be felt, as well as its great contribution to a constant and gradual improvement of the educational function, as it requires permanent and progressive qualification from the teacher. At each moment, flawed and inadequate practices are, through this process, replaced by others that are more profitable in achieving educational objectives.

Creative supervision: Its objective is, essentially, to stimulate people to creative action. It assumes that each teacher is an Education artist, connoting Art as a high quality of action, something that is created with originality, emotion, precision and harmony.

If the School must lead the student, as a priority, to reflection, criticism and creativity, this will not be done without identical demands on the educator. Certainly, the creative teacher discovers different ways to lead the student to creativity. On the contrary, the routine teacher will achieve this objective with great difficulty or, perhaps, will not achieve it at all.

It is essential that Supervision continually stimulates creativity, which will allow authentic professional growth. Using this type of supervision undoubtedly leads to teaching staff having more freedom; greater cooperation; greater commitment; greater progress in achieving objectives; greater satisfaction and consequent gratification for the work performed.

The exercise of creativity is the preservation, in the teacher's human person, of his basic qualities of intelligence and freedom, at the same time as a guarantee of quality for the educational action carried out by him.

Supervision was designed from the moment relations between man and work were established, considering that man's ability to carry out work should not be confused with the power of those who operate, as man is inserted in a society, its workforce is of an admirable nature, essentially and not interceded with another, just because it is human, creating profit. Hence the work was seen as a plurally technical point of view.

Historically, supervision in Brazil has been part of the educational process since its inception. The supervisor is the one who monitors, controls and directs the school's activities. He is capable of acting and thinking with intelligence, balance, leadership, authority, mastering theoretical knowledge and human relations.

In this sense, the ideal school becomes a social place that leads to hegemony, use, discrimination, and the prejudice of exclusion prevalent in society. Even in practice, supervision does not lose its function of strength and production. Modern techniques induce greater productivity at work by hiding such control and present themselves to the worker in the form of help, cooperation and solidarity. These forms characterize the modern management of human relations at work.

During “the inspection phase [of Supervision] there was greater concern regarding compliance with education laws, building conditions, legal status of teachers, compliance with dates and deadlines for school activities, such as exams, transfers, enrollments, vacations, documentation of students , etc. (NÉRICI, 1990, P.29).

This type of supervision followed strict standards throughout the country, with no consideration for the peculiarities and needs of each region, much less for the individual differences of students. During the 18th century and early 19th century, supervision remained within a line of inspecting, repressing, checking and monitoring. Only in 1881, in Cincinnatti , did the idea of supervision related to the teaching process emerge, and until 1875 it was focused primarily on verifying teaching activities. At the end of the 19th century, supervision became concerned with establishing well-defined standards of behavior and criteria for measuring academic performance, aiming at teaching efficiency. At the beginning of the 20th century, it was possible to see the use of scientific knowledge in improving teaching and measuring student learning results. Supervision then aims to transmit, explain, show, impose, judge and reward.

From 1925 onwards, a greater influence of behavioral sciences on supervision was noticed. Furthermore, there is a strong tendency to introduce democratic principles into educational organizations, applying them to the role of the supervisor as a democratic leader. Thus, the educational system was structured at three levels: Central, Regional and Local.

On the national scene, school supervision became a “mean function” that would guarantee the efficiency of the educational task, through controlling the productivity of teaching work. From this perspective, it was intended that supervision would constitute a technical service, independent of any political and ideological option, that is, a neutral service. With this, it interferes that supervision was imposed on education as a need for *modernization* and *technical assistance* , in order to guarantee the quality of teaching, but also, to ensure the hegemony of the dominant class understood as: With this character, supervision At school, a practice was developed focused on the techno-bureaucratic aspects of teaching, in which control was the main strategy that would ensure its reproductive role in Brazilian capitalist society.

Supervisor training is aimed at developing a conception of functionalist school supervision, a conception that perceives the school in a positive way, in which any change is seen as an imbalance in the homo-static state, therefore denying the dynamic character and evolution of the school institution and society.

Criticism of *functionalism* in supervision can make use of the technique, without the connotation of technicalism. It is, therefore, a function that, contextualized, inserts us into foundations and pedagogical processes, helping and promoting the coordination of the activities

of this process and its updating, through study and collective practices of teachers. It is with this type of conception that the 21st century begins. It is interesting to think that, with the implementation of national curricular parameters, educational supervision could be a great ally of the teacher in the application associated with the critical evaluation of these parameters, proving necessary that it be seen from a perspective based on participation, cooperation, integration and flexibility.

The supervisor's role is extremely important within the school. It becomes a catalytic element for the three vertices of teaching: teachers, students and staff. As a link between the three segments of teaching, you must have in-depth knowledge in academic (cultural), ethical and psychological-affective terms and always be ready to learn.

The supervisor must provide a friendly climate in the work environment: respect for the personality of the co-worker, value their production and performance, respect their limits and personal problems. The established interrelationship must be guided by empathy, security and mutual support. It must be vulnerable to malicious criticism, games of intrigue and the ill will of some, combined with the non-professionalism of others: absent, rude, careless, authoritarian teachers. You must remain above the nitpicking of work and remain free from distortions and conflicts. And be based on frankness developed through dialogue, exchanges *during* meetings between teachers and supervision. "The Supervisor needs, in addition to pedagogical training, knowledge of other areas (anthropology, philosophy, linguistics, sociology) and an in-depth understanding of other topics (aggression, sexuality, death, race and gender)" (MEDINA, 1997, p. 25) .

Therefore, it is essential to make the figure of the School Supervisor visible in contemporary times and establish an integrated relationship between his role in society and the activities he develops in day-to-day school life.

SCHOOL SUPERVISION: FUNCTION LINKED TO COLLECTIVE PARTICIPATION

With the arrival of digital technologies and their advances in the 21st century, the role of the School Supervisor within the educational context needs to undergo a technical and didactic reformulation. More than highlighting the differences in activities that this professional has in the different states of the country, we have to worry about a greater good, highlighting student learning and the processes linked to education.

The School Supervisor acts as a mediator and advisor in the planning, monitoring, guidance, evaluation and control of educational processes. It is necessary for it to be as transparent as possible in the demands and effects of implementing policies in schools, in participation in the definition of public educational policies, in articulation with other sectors of the State Secretariats, in the implementation of pedagogical and administrative management, in the valorization and in strengthening community participation channels and guiding school teams. Their competencies must be linked to an organization and the educational functioning of the school.

It is not enough to be just another educator, you must know and master the foundations and theories of the learning process, especially in valuing collective work and respecting individual differences. He needs to decentralize the educational system and always seek to make the expression quality of teaching something new and recover the time lost with the problems and make-believe in the educational area.

From the moment he starts to use education as one of the means of forming the integrity of character and moralization of citizens, he can reach the level of culture so desired by educational academies. This professional covers isolated points in the process: economy, politics, health and, finally, education. By inverting the action pyramid, you will then have the social success you so desire.

In this sense, it is the role of this professional to encourage cultural plurality, seeking to enable a school that recognizes its space within the limits of society, where the teaching/learning process focuses on the student's success, putting an end to the alchemists of knowledge and making the school, a center of scientific and professional knowledge, preparing students for life. He can no longer be part of the accommodating majority that allows itself to be carried away by the opposition Tunisian minority. It needs to reformulate ideas with well-defined and defined ideals, working on content that is significant for students and society. Planning and pedagogical design are crucial points to guide work in which the entire community must be involved and have the right to participate and give their opinion on matters of interest to them. We cannot let the 1980s be the only models of the educational system and seek to increasingly improve the models that underpinned education in the past.

The School Supervisor, in the pedagogical proposal, must establish goals that are linked to the school; reformulate educational projects and coordinate the development of a School Plan that is easy to understand and understand, with everyone's collaboration. You cannot let expressions of pressure still be the initial milestones for understanding and action within your workplace. You need to forget what you always hear in schools: it's better to do it tomorrow; I

can't come to the meeting in the afternoon; in lend me your planning; Let's do everything today, so tomorrow we will be free.

The construction of a pedagogical proposal must be linked to the collective, the effort and the responsible participation of those involved in the process. Planning and (re)planning are the means to achieve great success within the school. The daily life of a school can be constantly alive, as long as each educator looks for their actions to be a real action and not a ready-made recipe like those found in classroom textbooks. Building knowledge is also building actions, identifying causes and predicting effects; It's about learning a lot, rather than teaching yourself little.

In this sense, any and all academic production permeates the primary need to create a history that deserves to be taught and learned and, at each moment, we see that the need for the Supervisor to place himself before society as the driving force of this country becomes greater. makes it even more evident. You cannot let everything before education be the main reason for this to happen: salary policies and short-term economic adjustment; greater support for the democratic tradition and the end of marginalized populations, whose illiteracy is established, statistically, only by knowing how to write their own name, deceiving everyone with their insufficient theory of literacy. Just knowing the lyrics is not enough; It is necessary to have a critical sense , development and cultural maturation and that the cyclical stability of a free and democratic country is maintained, where democracy is also understood as education for all. The school and work project must contain the meaning and knowledge of a School Supervisor who is prepared to accompany you and establish parameters for the quality of teaching. As an articulator, he can focus on teaching/learning, without this country's educational plans being diluted in merely assistance projects.

In the management process, the Supervisor's role goes beyond those who define him as a simple conceptualizer of legal bases. It needs to be linked to a reality situation. You cannot condone the idea that school dropout is common; You must be aware that your role is also to seek ways to articulate these ways of producing and managing society. It needs to put an end to the vision of a welfare school, where offering an integral school is offering the illusion of guaranteeing basic quality standards, where transdisciplinarity can have its social role; overcome the barrier of repetition **and** dropout , not through decrees and other forms of automatic promotion, which encourage promotion without ensuring progress. You actually need to understand school failure in different sociocultural contexts; profoundly reformulate the school; support diagnoses about students; regularize the school flow; raise the quality standard as repetition rates decrease.

To this end, the exercise and autonomy of the educational system must go through the process of decentralization of information, through basic structures and quality services, through reflection on the role of the teacher and other professionals in the educational area, through public investments from and with quality in the retraining of professionals with consensus and parameters compatible with the educational ideal. Without these formal investitures, the Supervisor will never be able to become aware that the best way to establish the autonomy process is to be part of it responsibly. The greatest autonomy is in the classroom, because this is the only true place where everything begins. If the Supervisor thinks of this space as the beginning of an entire human evolution, he will come to believe that the advances will be beneficial. The School Supervisor must be inserted in the broader educational context, not just in closed offices as the supreme authority. You must be aware that the difference in strategies leads to part of the collective work action. Success is the result of knowledge, training, working conditions, technical assistance and collective efforts. You cannot play at teaching and the student pretends to be learning. Actions need to be effective and effective, with clear and supportive objectives for the development of any project. Nothing is more rewarding for the Supervisor than the certainty that his performance has undergone a clear and objective.

It is necessary to put an end to the idea of punitive suffering, fiasco and segregation of knowledge through pressure and horrors of fear. It is necessary to innovate these theories, to uproot the ideas that evaluating is synonymous with punishing from the most spurious circles. Well states Luckesi: evaluation is a qualitative assessment of relevant data from the teaching-learning process that helps the teacher to make decisions about your work. The vast majority of education professionals fail to understand that school assessment goes beyond the limits of the classroom and the School Supervisor usually sticks to interests others and not to the interests and realities of assessment. It is necessary to change this concept and get it right, definitively, so that the legacies received from the past are not left for a few more generations.

THE ROLE OF THE SCHOOL SUPERVISOR

The role of the school supervisor is, ultimately, the sum of efforts and actions undertaken with the aim of promoting the improvement of the teaching-learning process. This effort constantly focused on the teacher, in a process of assisting them and coordinating their action.

The assistance and coordination process has received varied approaches during the history of school supervision, such as, for example, the improvement of instructional materials; teaching methods, techniques and procedures ; curricular programs; the student assessment

process; the description of educational objectives; the student recovery process; of teacher performance.

According to Lück (1988)

Understanding the concept of management already presupposes, in itself, the idea of participation, that is, the associated work of people analyzing situations, deciding on their direction and acting on them *em conjunto*. It is because of the success of a set of its components, through the associated work, through reciprocity that creates a whole guided by a collective will (p. 168).

Although taking action aimed at the teacher, the school supervisor's actions were not always concerned with improving their performance. The concern for improving the teaching-learning process resulted, as a rule, in the effort to analyze some aspect of this process (any of those previously mentioned, with the exception of the teacher's performance), organize it, innovate it, feed it back, and hand it over to the teacher so he can apply it. And this constituted assistance to the teacher.

More recently, school supervision has gained a new dimension, more dynamic and with greater potential for long-term effectiveness: the improvement of teacher performance, that is, the development of their knowledge, skills and attitudes in relation to the teaching process. Aspects of instructional materials, methods, techniques, etc., become means or aspects of this development.

This line of action is in line with the statements made regarding the role of the teacher at school and the need to assist him to better perform this role. It directs school supervision to assume functions related to teacher training, in the most varied forms; observation and feedback on your performance; carrying out help interviews, both individually and in groups; holding meetings, etc.

The effectiveness of the school supervisor's action therefore becomes directly linked to his ability to promote behavioral changes in the teacher (KORAN, 1969); that is, the acquisition of new skills or reinforcement of existing ones; the development of new perspectives, ideas, opinions, attitudes, etc. This is because, ultimately, the improvement of the learning process, recommended by school supervision, does not depend so much on pre-established guidelines and ready-made plans, often little accepted, or passively accepted by the teacher, but on the conditions presented by this professional to implement them. It is the teacher's potential channeled into the learning process that makes a difference in this process (FOSTER, 1969), as already analyzed.

One of the greatest difficulties in education lies in the fact that proposed innovation ideas do not translate into action where education actually takes place: in the classroom. Sometimes, at the level of propositions, there is even a certain sophistication of ideas and methods. However, at the classroom level, the teacher is very commonly found acting guided by his intuition or, who knows, even by his exasperation at his perspective of hopelessness in the face of the difficulties he faces.

It can only be said that education improved when there was an improvement in the classroom, that is, in the way in which the teaching-learning process takes place. The teacher's performance in terms of his knowledge, attitudes and skills in relation to the teaching-learning process are the core of improving the quality of education and, as stated by Cogan (1973), much more than the improvement of buildings, teaching, methods and programs.

The lack of assistance to teachers regarding their performance in the classroom is considered by Cogan (1973) as one of the important causes of embarrassment in the educational process. Therefore, for the school supervisor to provide the teacher with a systematic assistance, in the sense of continuous performance.

NEED FOR SUPERVISION IN SCHOOLS

The actual concept of supervision is very contradictory these days. Currents of ideas take place in colleges, which follow American, French and Spanish authors and few follow Brazilian authors. It is due to the lack of succinct and objective analysis that the problem of training supervisors and applying positions did not happen.

The name supervisor evokes great supervision over matters related to teaching, from planning to guiding all elements of a school, diagnosing deficiencies and suggesting ways to resolve them, encouraging everyone to search for educational resources, achieving greater effectiveness in teaching process. Its functions are the most diverse, preparing new teachers, adaptations, integration into school life in all its areas; together with the director, on work standards and procedures with human and bureaucratic material; in the methods of valuing each one, within their function and directing the continuity of each one in a harmonious environment, of foresight and joint effort in the educational work.

The supervisor has been promoted and proclaimed as an element linked to administrative, bureaucratic and curricular work, making supervision a purely administrative function, preparing statistics, files, records, etc. Where it is not linked to all school activity, at all times, placing it as an accompaniment to the educational work in its various aspects.

The supervisor's work with other members of the school, it should be noted that without human relationships, no work will be possible. The beginning of any activity at school would be doomed to disaster, if barriers were not broken for any movement to try to resolve any teaching issue, administrative assistance to the principal and even the students' understanding of their role within the school. .

Imagine the situation in which a supervisor is given the task of working in a new school, both in the capital and in the interior. What action should you take initially? To avoid looking like a wolf, which would tear apart the rest of the pack, to those who are wary of its movements and interference (a stranger will want to give orders), here are several suggestions for starting activities to be followed and expanded. .

The first natural contact to be made is with the school director. It is considered essential to have a good appearance, friendliness, and locating aspects of the work you will perform in your establishment. You should not, at the beginning, show a thousand formulas, impetuosity, preponderance for the responsibility of your position, or show evidence that, in the future, you will want to be the master of the school. Never predict too much, but rather listen and consult the director in a pleasant and relaxed conversation, without hesitation or shyness, as if you were afraid of the work to be done.

Supervision is a technical-scientific task. As a technique, it is the defined way of carrying out a certain integral function of a system, in this case the educational one. The role of Supervision is important in achieving better quality in the provision of educational services, from the broadest and most comprehensive instances to the basic activity of the hour/class.

Although the Supervision function, with this name, is commonly exercised in operational teaching units (colleges, school groups, schools, etc.), in practice, with the new dimension of collegiate decision-making through work teams, Supervision is exercised (or at least it should be) by Coordination or Coordination teams at any operational level.

When analyzing the function as a technique, it is important to specify its dynamics: Supervision is a function that guarantees good quality and constant improvement of any service. Its essential characteristic is a critical dynamism, which is expressed in leading people to do things, evaluate them and return to better, more appropriate and productive actions.

The analysis of this brand already distinguishes this technique from many others, which are simply ways of doing things and, often, doing them automatically. Therefore, the Supervision technique must be adjectived, or better yet, Supervision itself must be adjectived: technical-scientific.

As a scientific work, Supervision has to research the facts to cover all dimensions of the reality in which it operates; establish action hypotheses; determine priorities with the respective activities necessary for their execution. Evaluate the results of changes that indicate the existence of a new reality and consequently impose a new cycle of action. Understood in this dimension, Supervision finds its great operational instrument in planning . All determining aspects of its essence of technical-scientific activity are guaranteed by planning.

In the history of the science of Planning, we must refer to the attempts to submit the scientific method to the study of social phenomena, with the aim of increasing man's predictive capacity and making a deliberate contribution to social progress. The concept of social evolution contains, within itself, the idea of Planning.

The idea of planning can be well understood considering that it originated from three sources: development of Administration science; development of economic theory; development theory. The historical application of this instrument was, without a doubt, pioneering in Russia, and for this reason, for several years, doubts persisted about its compatibility with the democratic experience. Today, the use of Planning within any political system is peaceful, although there are differences in decision-making aspects, level of centralization, etc.

The awareness of the need for systematic planning of Education is of recent origin. It has aroused great interest, as evidenced by studies and conclusions from several international meetings. Like any part of social conditioning, Education is a complex process in which pedagogical, economic, political, administrative and cultural aspects meet and closely interrelate. Educational planning will not be possible without taking into account all these aspects. This forces openness to interdisciplinary teams, while at the same time alerting to the need, already explored in the previous chapter, for an overview of the socio-economic context by the educator and, mainly, by specialists and generalists in Education.

Within these reflections (incomplete due to the extent and complexity of the subject, as well as its intended use for educators and not Planning technicians), which constitute basic approaches to the perception of Planning as a process in constant development, an attempt is made, not a definition, but of providing conceptualization elements.

Planning is a prior discipline of an action, simple or complex, aiming at pre-established results, through rational activities, minimum effort for maximum results, using all available resources. It is a complex function that involves conceptual, methodological and operational problems . The entire planning process is carried out through phases determined according to a

systematization although, in practice, such division is artificial. The planning phases are as follows:

Diagnosis: quantification and qualification of the situation in terms of needs ; objectivity in assessing the efficiency of the current project, as well as existing potential capacity; realization in the greatest amplitude, reaching the whole and all possible and determining interrelations;

Schedule: definition of global objectives and explanation of educational objectives;

Goal setting: quantification of objectives compatible with financial and human resources; formulation of the successive steps of the action with details of the activities;

Execution: practical implementation involving the aspects determined in the programming;

Assessment: it depends on the former and the continuity of the planning process is basic.

ABOUT PLANNING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTION

Due to the aforementioned lack of planning mentality, there is a great risk in implementing Planning. Mainly in the educational field , where facts such as lack of commitment to results, intuition and, in many cases, the small size of the operational unit are found. AND the risk of planning not constituting a working instrument, but simply a fulfillment of orders or determinations from decision-makers. And, perhaps it is a simple *wordy filling out* of an alien model of which a copy is kept *in the drawer* , as proof of the task completed by sending the original to the Service headquarters. Such an attitude should not be simplistically condemned, but analyzed from several angles, in an attempt to find a solution, mentalization and empowerment. Otherwise , accusations of arbitrary, meaningless and apparently sadistic measures will remain, and at an increasing pace, on the one hand... and, on the other, a possible source of discouragement to fight in a true sense of *countercurrent* .

Like all skills that must be integrated into efficient action, this one also needs to be experienced existentially, models are not enough. It is a challenge for educational leaders, as it is a new behavior that must be trained, and changing behavior is neither simple nor easy. It is necessary to break habitual response patterns. It is necessary to shake the subject, undermine his security so that, realizing his state of imbalance, he seeks new ways of adapting. When talking about Planning, this is evident, because for the vast majority Planning is a superfluous function because it is theoretical, because it is unnecessary within their usual schemes of action,

which (to be fair!) have often been valid by the force of the great and versatile power of human intuition. However, it is not rational to leave such an important and determining role in human destinies to the almost adventure of getting it right by intuition, when one should take advantage of the values of intuition in the almost safe path of Planning. Consider, also, all the marks of our historical formation, in which the *command-obedience relationship was predominantly established*, not contributing to the development of reflection and decision-making skills with consequent compromised behavior.

It is necessary to reflect on how to introduce Planning as a work tool, as the first *pragmatic action* of any undertaking. It has already been highlighted that this is a new behavior and, therefore, it must be remembered that only after much experience as a participant in a process will one be able to begin to infer, only then will the theory make sense, otherwise it will be empty language that, for this very reason, does not achieve communication.

In this aspect, Supervision has a great asset, in terms of helping to raise awareness of the value of Planning through its constant use, when carried out. Return to Planning, handle it, organize bulletin boards of planned activities (action schedules), help with the constant evaluation of what was planned.

Regarding the need for Planning, both in the specific Supervision function itself and in all Services subject to said Supervision, it becomes evident that there are different levels of Planning whether referring to Education or involved in it.

The National Education Legislation must be the basis of any and all system planning programming. It's certainly the obvious; but, for those I read on the front lines, the practice shows a real lack of knowledge of the legislation. There is a current tendency to correct this anomaly, through systematic and repeated dissemination of Law 5,692/71. It is clear that there is a need for mentalization so that the educational law takes effect in the day-to-day work of each teacher. A response to the educational problem based on orders would be simplistic; one should not attribute mythical value to the law itself, however good it may be.

For knowledge and guarantee of unity and reinforcement of educational action regarding National Legislation, the part of the Brazilian Constitution regarding Education can be established as an acceptable minimum; the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB), No. 4,024/61, which was not amended by Law 5,692/71, which establishes guidelines and bases for 1st and 2nd grade education. Once again, it should be noted that the objective is not limited to knowledge of the laws or their interpretation, as specialists exist for that purpose. That the habit of support be structured, of starting from the Law as a philosophy and general principles to guide programming and activities, whatever they may be.

With this, we observe the gravity, wrapped in humor, of popular acquiescence to the fact that *laws in Brazil are made but are not enforced* ; at the same time that the hypothesis is raised about the possible consequences of the attitude recommended here, if experienced at all levels and sectors. It will be possible to not only comply with laws; but, what is more important, enable greater popular contingents to interfere in legislative processes, which is vital in any democratic regime.

THE SUPERVISOR AS AN AGENT OF CHANGE

The forwarding of ideas about leadership, in a work on School Supervision , to the mounting of the challenge proposed above, is not disinterested, casual or unaddressed. Quite the contrary, this challenge is directly addressed to the Supervisor. He must become an agent of change, in the sense of dynamizing group work, in the different instances of his action. To do this, he must be a *functional leader* , responsible, first and foremost, for motivating and developing leadership in all his groups.

Everything exposed in the previous chapter, mainly aspects relating to the complexity of the human problem and the way of helping people, are basic points in the training and performance of the Supervisor. All modern Supervision treaties focus on aspects such as the climate of dialogue, the growth situation of the people involved, the basic importance of personal approaches, the quality of interactions between the people involved, the importance of feeling like a person and, as such, helped in their role. IT IS a whole dimension of working with people that constitutes the focus of the Supervisor's work. This requires, in addition to knowledge and work methodology, aspects of integrity and personality maturity. There is no shortage of treatises with exhaustive lists of qualities appropriate to the role of the educator and, as such, necessary for the Supervisor.

This statement is more than obvious, since the Supervisor's role is to contribute to the Teacher's training. And today it is impossible to perform this function simply by using the too simplistic process of dictating standards. There is an urgent need for the support of expected behavior on the part of the Supervisor. As always, without denying the validity of the exposition and justification of these qualities always found in any pedagogical manual, we prefer not to mention them. Stereotypical nomenclatures often contribute to theoretical recitation, which, although it does not prevent it, does not require existential authenticity.

The Supervisor must be encouraged to discover in the most diverse ways the great importance of his attitudes in determining the quality of his work. As an educational leader, as

responsible for the experience of groups at different levels of their activity, he must always reformulate his concepts and must evaluate his performance.

Facts that exist in everyone involved in the pedagogical work of supervision: Irresponsibility, ignorance, stupidity, indiscipline, misunderstanding, self-indulgence, communication difficulties, personal problems, poor human relationships, temperament, difficulties in listening and accepting, psychological complexes, disinterest, lack of motivation, family and educational conditions, transfer of problems, lack of awareness, natural antipathies, relaxation, disloyalty.

Such facts require the Supervisor to have an attitude of understanding and respect for the human person. You must discover ways to awaken people's needs for different behaviors. These facts constitute a challenge to the Supervisor's capacity as an agent of change: facts arising from the Supervision situation with other leaders, difficulty in joint planning, clash of leaders.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

To better understand school supervision, its trajectory was based, and it is important to consider that supervision must, first of all, change mentality, which, in turn, will reflect on us several processes that are interconnected in their essence.

Thus, a true vicious circle appears: lack of resources, deficiencies in the educational process, lack of training and qualifications for work. In this situation, Education undoubtedly has a specific role to play. And the efficient fulfillment of this function is the great challenge for school supervision.

Such revelations show that school supervision must be based on the recognition of its need. An analysis of the current world highlights new demands in human society. In this analysis, a general and comprehensive characteristic will be the observation of a changing world.

It is therefore analyzed that supervision is a process that must adapt to the various circumstances of school work. In the different modalities of action, it must always identify difficulties, helping them. After carrying out the research, it became even more evident that school supervision is of paramount importance in achieving better quality in the provision of educational services, from the broadest levels and comprehensive down to the basic activity of the hour/class.

The school should enable everyone's participation, as there is a need to awaken the potential of teachers. School where there is true leadership, energizing groups to guarantee work together, because the school supervisor lives according to a dichotomy of administrative procedure and always seeks to be on the side of school communities, trying to isolate the simplistic function of *legis funciones*, ready to consolidate a supportive democratic management and guide standardization.

Under the assumption of centralizing authoritarianism, the division of activities increases differences and distances between segments of society and the effective reasons for education. It is necessary to put an end to the supervisor-directed trinomial, with the participation of supervisors being a sedimentation of decisions. The School Supervisor must be the element that needs to be in the leadership of administration services, acting within specific parameters and with activities aimed at acting as supervisors (advisors) of the educational process.

There is no way to let the history of education pass without having been part of it. The School Supervisor must be at the forefront of citizenship actions, seeking quality for the school, as the agency responsible for training citizens, developing their skills and skills to transform society and provide hegemony for a more just and supportive society.

It cannot just be within the limits of the middle system of Education Departments, it needs to expand its world view, seek a solidary partnership of political and social awareness. The School Supervisor must have a more participatory role, an essentially ethical transformation, not so fond of extreme bureaucratic work, making theory stop being a simple role taking and start using praxis as a rule.

The School Supervisor is the professional who:

- Read, study and decode educational, criminal, civil and administrative legislation, the Statute of Children and Adolescents, the regulations of the Association of Parents and Teachers, the Student Union, the School Council, the School Canteen, the janitorial staff, the terms for the transfer of school buildings and others, to provide support and subsidies for the School Director;
- Reads and draws up schemes relating to solutions, deliberations, indications and opinions issued by competent bodies (Education Departments, National, State or Municipal Education Councils and others), to guide school directors, prepare technical guidelines for teacher-coordinators, swimmers and teachers;
- Studies standards on the construction of school buildings, positioning of fire extinguishers, security, floor plans of school buildings, legislation pertinent to the issuance of

technical reports, to comply with legislation regarding the authorization, installation and operation of non-state schools and maintenance of state school buildings;

➤ Participates in team work , study sessions, committees to evaluate appeals filed by students, parents of students, teachers and other segments of society;

➤ Analyzes school regulations, course plans, changes to regulations, addenda to school regulations, change of address of private school units, payment reversals and other matters;

➤ Is part of an investigation committee to investigate facts and reports of irregularities in the educational field;

➤ It provides equivalence of studies for students who completed primary and secondary education abroad. Therefore, you have to know the education system of other countries, the most diverse: Korea, Yugoslavia, Mercosur countries, others in Latin America, Switzerland, Bosnia, etc.;

➤ He works in central Government bodies, together with the pedagogical workshop, providing philosophical support and assistance to the area in which he eventually graduates (Biology, Sciences, Chemistry, Portuguese Language).

Thus, the School Supervisor is the professional who is always present, fulfilling his social and professional role and living a reality, while many imagine all these theories on an empirical level. It is up to them to analyze the situation to determine which form of action is most appropriate to the reality in which they will work. They must always bear in mind that democratic activity, involving everyone who participates in it, is always more positive, as being a *specialist* means dedicating yourself to the specific issues of your work, knowledge, training and practice, as parts of a whole, that is, of a Common Project.

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